

1. INTRODUCTION

Hydrogen storage in the mobility sector predominantly relies on high-pressure tanks, particularly Type IV Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels (COPVs), which combine carbon-fibre composites with thermoplastic liners. While effective, conventional thermoset resin matrices present challenges regarding its poor recyclability. Replacing them with thermoplastic matrices enhances sustainability, facilitates reparability, which ultimately may lead to reduced lifecycle costs.

2. AIM

To develop a **fully thermoplastic Type IV pressure vessel rated for 700 bar**, using an innovative manufacturing technology. The vessel will integrate **embedded fiber Bragg grating (FBG) optical sensors** for **real-time structural health monitoring** during testing and fuelling and defueling.

3. METHODOLOGY

The development of the thermoplastic COPV followed the **ISO 19881:2018 standard** which specifies requirements for onboard gaseous hydrogen storage in vehicles. This includes safety and service conditions, material selection, design, manufacturing, testing, and periodic inspections using non-destructive methods.

MATERIAL SELECTION & CHARACTERIZATION	WINDING PATTERN DEVELOPMENT	STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS (FEA)	MANUFACTURING & PROCESS OPTIMIZATION (AFP)	PROTOTYPE FABRICATION & TESTING
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Selection of suitable thermoplastic materials Perform mechanical characterization 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Design fiber winding architectures Simulate and refine patterns for strength and manufacturability 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Conduct Finite Element Analysis Target burst pressure: 1575 bar 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Implement Automated Fiber Placement (AFP) Use IR laser source for thermoplastic tape heat and consolidation Apply Design of Experiments (DOE) to optimize process parameters 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Manufacture prototype using optimized process Embedment of FBG sensors Conduct validation tests (burst & cyclic testing) Monitor structural integrity using embedded FBG sensors

4. PROJECT CONSTRAINTS AND CHALLENGES

Thermoplastic Liner	Metallic Boss	Composite Overwrap
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermoplastic material with low hydrogen permeation coefficient (e.g. HDPE or PA); Thermoplastic material compatible with Rotomoulding process for Liner Manufacturing; Liner material must have a good mechanical properties and high thermal and dimensional stability within -40°C to +85°C. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Material must be compatible with gaseous hydrogen (e.g. S31603, Al6061); Must have a strong adhesion with the thermoplastic liner material; Good mechanical integration into the thermoplastic liner. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Thermoplastic Carbon-Reinforced UD tapes compatible with AFP in-house system; Thermoplastic matrix with T_g ≥ 105°C (accord. to ISO 19881:2018); Thermoplastic matrix compatible with the liner base material; Design winding patterns that comply with the maximum burst pressure (2,25 x 70MPa = 157.5 MPa – accord. ISO 19881:2018).

5. TANK SPECIFICATIONS

Table 1. Design specifications for the COPV.

Fully-thermoplastic Type IV COPV - Design Specifications		
Target Working Pressure	70	MPa
Tank Geometry	Cylindrical with semi-elliptical domes	
Tank Diameter	296	mm
Boss Diameter	65	mm
Length-to-diameter (L/D) ratio	3	
Internal volume capacity	≈ 54	L
Design Safety Factor	2.25	
Maximum Burst Pressure (P _b)	157.5	MPa
Liner material	PA11	
Boss material	Al6061-T6	
Composite tape material	UD Carbon-Fiber thermoplastic PPA tape	

PROJECT FLOWCHART

COMPOSITE OVERWRAP PRESSURE VESSEL PRODUCTION

AUTOMATED FIBER PLACEMENT (AFP) FOR TAPE WINDING

FULLY-THERMOPLASTIC TYPE IV COPV

PROJECT STATUS & FUTURE WORKS

This work is currently under development under the HI_MOV project umbrella. The safety and service requirements, as well as the COPV modeling, material selection, and characterization, are complete. Structural numerical simulations will be conducted to the full optimization of the composite shell for the target burst pressure (P_b). Once this phase is complete, the COPV with integrated sensorization will be manufactured, followed by experimental validation, through burst testing, to confirm its ability to withstand the projected pressures.

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¹Rocha H, Antunes P, Lafont U, Nunes JP. Processing and structural health monitoring of a composite overwrapped pressure vessel for hydrogen storage. *Structural Health Monitoring*. 2023;23(4):2391-2406. DOI:10.1177/1475921723120422.
²W., Thomas, B., Christian; H., Christian; Thermal skin effect in laser-assisted tape placement of thermoplastic composites. *Dissertation / PhD Thesis, RWTH Aachen University*, 2019; DOI: 10.18154/RWTH-2019-06638